

PROFESSIONAL FAULTS IN THE ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article explores the complexity and nuance of pedagogical errors that often go unrecognized by educators. It also addresses errors related to pedagogical strategies and discusses methods for correcting mistakes in the planning of educational activities.*

Keywords: *pedagogical mistake, cooperation, tactical errors, pedagogical process, educational material, professional approach, scientific phenomenon.*

Errors are a typical phenomenon that occurs in all areas of human activity. Therefore, any pedagogical activity is not free from mistakes, but it is observed that the cost of mistakes made in this field is very expensive for others, and it is painful. Because pedagogical mistakes can cause tragic consequences for a whole person (child).

The complexity and subtlety of the pedagogical error is characterized by the fact that the pedagogue does not realize it in most cases. It is this situation that does not leave the possibility to prevent it or draw a correct conclusion from it. By the time the consequences of a mistake become apparent, it is too late to correct the mistake, or it becomes obvious that it will have no effect.

Mistakes can be made in the form of actions, habits, reactions during cooperation with students during the period of predicting the future pedagogical activity, as well as during the implementation of the direct pedagogical process.

Errors in the strategy (prediction) of pedagogical activity include errors in goal setting and errors in planning the educational process.

Errors related to setting pedagogical goals:

1. As a result of teacher's failure to properly understand the essence of pedagogical activity, the lesson process is carried out without certain predetermined goals, as a result, the training is organized on the basis of a random goal that arose directly in the course of the lesson, and extremely low efficiency in education is achieved.

As a result of the inconsistency of methodological goals, achieving a low quality-indicator through the failure of logical connections at different stages of the lesson is occurred.

The reasons for the recognized errors are characterized by the inability of the pedagogue to plan his training clearly and carefully in advance, that is, the inability to set specific internal educational and pedagogical goals.

In order to prevent such mistakes, the pedagogue should first of all have a perfect knowledge of his specialty, secondly, a deep understanding of the spiritual life of society and social tasks, thirdly, he should know the interests of children well and be able to direct them to educational goals, and most importantly, he should be able to perfectly define the goals of educational activities. For this, the teacher will have to be specially engaged in mastering the methodology of setting educational goals.

Errors in Pedagogical Planning and Their Implications

Errors in pedagogical planning are often closely linked to mistakes in setting educational goals and frequently occur simultaneously. It is beneficial to conduct a thorough analysis of these errors to understand their true nature and categorize them into distinct groups.

Types of Pedagogical Errors

Tactical errors in teaching include mistakes related to pedagogical interactions, communication, and organization, as well as deviations from professional etiquette. These errors can be categorized as follows:

1. **Methodological Errors:** These errors arise from issues related to the teaching methods used. They may include confusion in explaining the subject matter, a lack of systematic presentation, overly complex or overly simplistic explanations, emotional delivery that affects learning, poor time management during lessons, and improper use of educational methods and tools.

2. **Errors in Managing Educational Activities:** These involve problems with organizing and guiding students' learning activities during lessons.

Methodological Errors

Methodological errors, as identified by experts like V.I. Juravlev in "Basics of Pedagogical Conflictology," are significant because they are recognized by students. Juravlev highlights specific issues, such as indecision when evaluating students' knowledge. Common problems noted by students include:

- Teachers requiring students to answer in specific formats or ways without accommodating individual responses.

- Assigning poor grades without understanding the reasons behind incomplete homework.

- Providing excessive criticism or long lectures for incorrect answers or deviations from the expected response.

Students also express dissatisfaction due to:

- Unexpected quizzes or tests without prior notice.

- Lack of tolerance for jokes or off-topic responses, leading to teachers' angry reactions.

- Issues with homework checks and requests.

Critique of Pedagogical Practices

Historically, pedagogues like V.N. Soroka-Rosinsky criticized educators who, despite good intentions, employed untested methods without proper guidance from school authorities or experienced colleagues. Such educators often make arbitrary changes to the curriculum, using personal outlines or methods instead of established textbooks and recommended materials. This approach reflects a tendency to implement non-standard methods without proper validation.

Recommendations for Addressing Pedagogical Errors

To prevent and correct pedagogical mistakes, educators should consider the following strategies:

1. **Critical Reflection:** Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of teaching methods and approaches. Develop the habit of self-reflection and view your practice from an external perspective.

2. **Continuous Learning:** Stay informed by studying pedagogical, psychological, and methodological literature. Avoid over-relying on personal experience and ensure your practices are grounded in scientific principles.

3. **Maintain an Error Log:** Keep a record of mistakes as valuable learning tools. Regularly review these entries to avoid repeating past errors.

4. **Embrace Mistakes:** Understand that making mistakes is a part of the learning process. Foster a mindset open to new ways of thinking and problem-solving.

5. **Formulate Alternative Solutions:** Be prepared to devise alternative strategies based on a thorough assessment of educational situations.

6. **Avoid Routines and Stereotypes:** Resist the tendency to follow established routines or blindly mimic others. Critically analyze all information and advice before accepting or implementing it.

7. **Protect Against Negative Influence:** Do not let others' negativity or personal problems affect your own teaching practice. Recognize that such behavior often stems from individual issues rather than professional inadequacies.

8. **Persevere and Develop:** Do not be discouraged by mistakes. Continuously enhance your theoretical and intellectual capabilities.

9. **Learn from Experienced Educators:** Observe and learn from the practices of seasoned teachers to gain insights into effective methods and creative approaches.

By following these recommendations, educators can improve their pedagogical practices, reduce errors, and enhance their effectiveness in classroom. Pedagogues, who are masters of their profession, try not to make mistakes at all or to reduce them as much as possible. The teacher, as a subject of the educational process, regularly performs the activities of solving problems and tasks of various nature and complexity related to the content of education. It is impossible to be completely free from errors. However, it is possible to teach the teacher to behave correctly in real pedagogical conditions, to warn of possible mistakes and conflict situations or to prevent them.

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